

PEACE AND JUSTICE PEDAGOGIES IN ISRAELI-PALESTINIAN YOUTH INTEGRATION PROGRAMS

Eliyahu David Tchelet

School of Social Work, Hebrew University of Jerusalem.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20041186>

ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>Peace education has become an essential domain for addressing conflict, fostering reconciliation, and promoting inclusive societies. While theoretical frameworks such as Allport's Contact Hypothesis emphasize the role of sustained intercultural interaction in reducing prejudice, contemporary peace education has expanded to encompass pedagogical models that integrate civic engagement, environmental awareness, and critical consciousness. Despite the centrality of pedagogy in shaping program outcomes, the ways in which teaching methods are selected, adapted, and implemented remain underexplored in scholarly literature. This study examines pedagogical practices within Israeli-Palestinian youth programs, highlighting how content, ideology, and instructional strategies interact to influence participant experiences. Drawing on existing research in comparative and civic education, the analysis underscores the potential and limitations of different teaching approaches in promoting meaningful dialogue, empathy, and pluralistic engagement across divided communities. Findings suggest that while direct contact can disrupt stereotypes and build understanding, the success of such interventions critically depends on careful pedagogical design that negotiates ideological tensions and creates space for genuine intercultural learning. By foregrounding the pedagogical dimension, this study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of how peace education initiatives can effectively foster justice, mutual understanding, and transformative social learning.</p>	<p>Peace Education, Pedagogy, Israeli-Palestinian Youth, Intergroup Dialogue, Conflict Resolution</p>

Introduction

Peace education has emerged as a vital and evolving field of scholarship, shaped over decades by efforts to address conflict, foster reconciliation, and envision more just and inclusive societies (Pineda, Celis, & Rangel, 2019). At its core, peace education seeks not only to reduce violence but to cultivate the conditions for meaningful understanding across lines of difference (Bajaj, 2015). Among its most influential theoretical foundations is Allport's Contact Hypothesis (1954), which suggests that, under specific conditions, sustained intercultural interaction can mitigate prejudice and transform intergroup relations. While this framework continues to underpin many programs that emphasize dialogue and interpersonal engagement, the field has broadened to include pedagogical models centered on environmental sustainability, civic participation, and critical consciousness, all

approaches that do not necessarily depend on direct contact. Despite the promise of joint encounters in disrupting stereotypes and fostering empathy, their success hinges on the pedagogical choices that structure them (Ross, 2017). Yet, as our review indicates, this pedagogical dimension remains relatively underexamined within peace education scholarship (Akar, 2016). As Ross (2019) cautions, efforts to promote dialogue are often constrained by internal ideological "red lines," particularly in contexts where ethno-national identities intersect, and sometimes clash, with broader activist commitments, limiting the scope for genuinely pluralistic engagement.

While the general academic fields of pedagogy and teaching practices are well-established (Nind et al., 2016), a literature gap exists regarding the application of different teaching methods in peace education programs. Building on previous studies that examined pedagogy in the field of comparative education (Alexander, 2001) and civic education (Cohen, 2018), we aimed to explore not only the ideologies and content that influenced peace education initiatives but also how these approaches were implemented and enacted in practice.

In Israel, efforts to improve relations between Jews and Palestinians through organized educational encounters began as early as the 1950s (Maoz, 2011). However, most youth had no interactions with Palestinians outside these programs (Daaroushe, 2015). Since the 1990s, programs such as Seeds of Peace, Peace Child Israel, and Neve Shalom/Wahat al-Salaam have developed extensive educational models. Lazarus (2015), drawing on two decades of empirical research, documents the long-term trajectories of peace education participants, highlighting a pattern of initial attitudinal change, decline upon reentry into everyday conflictual realities, and the potential for restoration through sustained engagement. These findings illustrate both the enduring promise and the limitations of peace education in deeply divided settings. While the Israeli-Palestinian conflict remains an identity-based and structurally entrenched conflict, it is shaped by asymmetrical power relations, systemic inequalities, and deeply rooted national narratives, rendering it exceptionally difficult to resolve (Bar-Tal, 2007). Therefore, it presents a compelling case for a deeper understanding of the role of pedagogy in justice-oriented educational initiatives. Our primary research question is: What are the challenges and opportunities inherent in different pedagogical approaches within peace education programs designed for Israeli and Palestinian youth? We argue that such programs face significant challenges in translating their ideological goals into effective pedagogical practices. By examining the diverse approaches adopted by various organizations, this research demonstrates that education for peace, justice, and democratic citizenship necessitates continuous reflection on both content and pedagogical methods.

Theoretical Framework

Pedagogy and teaching practices encompass both methods of study and forms of discourse, integrating instructional actions, theories, and debates shaped by societal culture and educational objectives (Alexander, 2001). Such notions emphasize the balance between content delivery, student engagement, and adaptability to diverse needs, all of which represent critical challenges examined in this study. Moreover, this framework highlights the importance of aligning teaching strategies with ideological commitments.

In the context of peace education, pedagogy serves mainly as a means to address various forms of conflict and violence within diverse social contexts (Bajaj, 2015). Central to its mission is the promotion of reconciliation and the establishment of sustainable peace by constructing narratives that bridge differing perspectives. Within this scholarly field, two prominent pedagogical models relevant to our study emerge: the indirect model and the direct model (Bar-Tal & Rosen, 2009). The indirect model emphasizes reflective thinking, tolerance, ethno-empathy, and conflict-resolution skills, aiming to cultivate openness, critical thinking, and empathy while equipping learners with the necessary tools to navigate conflicts. In contrast, the direct model explicitly engages participants

in confronting conflict-related issues, employing pedagogical strategies to reshape beliefs, attitudes, and social behaviors central to the conflict.

The direct approach builds on Allport's (1954) contact theory, a widely recognized framework for reducing intergroup prejudice. This theory posits that group dialogue can significantly reduce negative stereotypes and prejudices among group members when four key pedagogical conditions are met: equality of social status among participants, meaningful interpersonal interaction between members of both groups, cooperation toward shared goals, and opportunities for sustained, long-term social engagement rather than temporary collaboration. Allport's students (Paluck et al., 2017) further refined these conditions by highlighting the importance of institutional support and alignment with legal frameworks. However, in the context of expanded conflict, this approach has evolved to include intentional dialogue about the conflict itself, a pedagogical element not emphasized in Allport's original formulation but developed in response to the complexities of intractable conflict settings.

In addition to these traditional pedagogical models that emphasize structured dialogue and reconciliation (Bar-Tal & Rosen, 2009), recent scholarship has introduced the concept of Peace Process Pedagogy (PPP), which focuses on the emotional and psychological barriers to peace education (Gomez-Suarez, 2017). This approach suggests that effective peace pedagogy must actively counteract misinformation, dismantle entrenched narratives, and acknowledge the emotional dimensions of engagement with structural and identity-based conflict. Similarly, Savard (2018) contends that peace education should move beyond fostering interpersonal harmony to cultivate critical consciousness and promote social action aimed at dismantling structural inequities. These frameworks push peace education beyond interpersonal reconciliation by centering structural violence and systemic injustice as key sites of pedagogical intervention.

In recent years, critical peace education scholars have questioned the dominance of psychologized and interpersonal approaches to peacebuilding that overlook structural injustices (Bekerman, 2007; Higgins & Novelli, 2020; Kester, 2018; Kester & Cremin, 2017; Zembylas & Bekerman, 2013). These critiques challenge the field's reliance on the contact hypothesis and liberal-humanist assumptions, arguing that such frameworks often serve as depoliticizing tools that obscure power asymmetries and material conditions. Drawing on diverse contexts, including Israel-Palestine, these scholars propose alternative paradigms grounded in cultural political economy, transrational epistemologies, and second-order reflexivity.

While many Israeli-Palestinian peace education programs have focused on dialogue and interpersonal transformation, critics have noted that these often sidestep deeper structural inequalities and the realities of ongoing occupation (Bekerman & Zembylas, 2011; Maoz, 2011). Tapper (2015), drawing on Freire's critical pedagogy, argues that such programs risk reinforcing the status quo when they avoid politicizing content or neglect power asymmetries. He calls for pedagogies that confront systems of oppression rather than seek to "balance" narratives, emphasizing that true peace education must be rooted in the lived realities and political agency of its participants. This framing helps distinguish between pedagogical approaches that promote coexistence through neutrality and those that pursue transformation through critique and political clarity. This critical turn informs our analysis of pedagogical models in peace education by underscoring how pedagogical choices can either reproduce or resist dominant ideologies and institutional constraints.

Thus, building on prior research that investigates the relationship between pedagogical approaches and peace education (Arató & Bodnár, 2024), this theoretical framework highlights the critical importance of exploring diverse teaching strategies. Such strategies provide key insights into how educational practices can meaningfully engage with conflict and promote reconciliation. By analyzing these pedagogical approaches, this study advances

a deeper understanding of the dynamic interplay between content, method, and the pursuit of social transformation. In this context, our research questions and findings align with existing discussions of both direct and indirect peace education models (Maoz, 2011; Shonfeld, 2024). At the same time, we introduce a sociocultural curricular perspective that foregrounds political reflection as central to the pedagogical enactment of socially engaged and justice-oriented educational practices.

Methodology

To address our primary research question on the pedagogical practices employed in four Israeli-Palestinian peace education programs, we adopted a multiple case study (Stake, 1995) qualitative research approach (Marshall & Rossman, 2010).

Sample and Participants

The sample of four organizations selected for this study was identified through purposive sampling (Harsh, 2011) following consultations with academic experts in the field. This approach ensured an informed selection process aimed at capturing a diverse range of educational practices. The selected organizations intentionally adopted diverse educational methodologies while maintaining a unified focus on promoting peace education among youth, specifically targeting students from middle school through high school. One organization ceased communication after a single interview was conducted. While this organization is not included as a core case study, the interview data are still analyzed and treated separately from the three main cases. Thus, below we present the three peace education organizations that formed the main focus of our study and the individuals affiliated with each. To preserve confidentiality and adhere to ethical standards, all organization and participant names are pseudonyms.

Friends for Peace. A joint Jewish-Palestinian initiative focused on facilitating youth encounters and civic engagement.

- Deborah (Jewish), Co-Director
- Lana (Palestinian), Co-Director
- Yael (Jewish), School Liaison and Mentor Supervisor

Peace Flowers. An educational nonprofit that designs and implements encounter-based programs for Jewish and Palestinian youth.

- Meir (Jewish), Pedagogical Director
- Noor (Palestinian), Former Instructor
- Sylvie (Jewish American), Instructor

Peace Hill. A regional dialogue and leadership initiative working primarily in mixed cities and shared public spaces.

- Daoud (Palestinian), Facilitator and Program Coordinator
- Mor (Jewish), Instructor
- Miri (Jewish), Director

All organizations included in this study bring together Jewish and Palestinian citizens of Israel, all residing within the 1948 borders (Green Line). While the Palestinian participants identify themselves nationally and culturally as Palestinians, they hold Israeli citizenship and are often referred to in Israeli public discourse as "Israeli Arabs." The organizations studied here do not include participants from the West Bank or Gaza Strip.

Data Collection

The research spanned a year and included semi-structured interviews, observations, and collection and analysis of program details, protocols, outputs, and additional materials from the organizations. The data for this study

were collected before the escalation of armed conflicts that began on October 7, 2023. This context is crucial for interpreting the findings, as they reflect conditions and perspectives prior to these recent events. Nevertheless, the implications of the study may provide critical insights into the challenges and opportunities present in the current harsh climate.

The study included ten semi-structured interviews with instructors and officials from four informal peace education organizations working with Jewish and Palestinian youth. Three instructors or officials were interviewed from each organization, along with one additional interview conducted with an instructor from an organization that ceased contact following the initial meeting. We aimed to conduct interviews as diversely as possible, interviewing both men and women, where applicable, as well as both Palestinians and Jews from each organization, rather than focusing on just one group.

The interviews were conducted individually using a pre-constructed, semistructured interview format (see appendix). The interviews were recorded and fully transcribed by Tutman. At the beginning of each interview, the research and ethical guidelines were explained to the interviewees. Additionally, six full-day observations were conducted across the organizations during key activity days. Documents were also collected from each organization, including mission statements, pedagogical materials, and records of meetings.

Data Analysis

We conducted a thematic analysis following an inductive, iterative process (Saldaña, 2009) using the Atlas.ti Web software (see Figure 1). First, all interviews, observations and documents were transcribed, organized and reviewed for accuracy. We then engaged in open coding, identifying initial codes that reflected patterns of meaning in the data. These codes were refined and clustered into broader themes through repeated readings, ongoing analytic memos, and collaborative discussions among the research team. Both authors were involved in the data analysis process, with Cohen contributing academic expertise and extensive prior experience in qualitative analysis to help shape the interpretive framework. While we remained attentive to concepts from the literature, our coding framework emerged primarily from the data rather than being imposed a priori. The themes that guided our cross-case analysis, such as dialogue, resistance, political asymmetry, and pedagogical intent, thus evolved through recursive engagement with the empirical material.

Ethical Considerations

All participants signed a consent form agreeing to participate in the study, which was approved by the joint ethics committee of the Faculty of the Humanities, the Faculty of Law, and the School of Education at The Hebrew University of Jerusalem. The identities of the participants and the organizations in which they act are confidential, with personal details removed and any identifying information altered.

Positionality

Tutman is a young Israeli woman, a traditional Ashkenazi Jew of European and South American descent, and an educator committed to Israel's younger generation. Conducting this research as part of her graduate studies, her identity as an educator aligns with the study's focus on pedagogical practices. Her cultural heritage and teaching experience shape her perspective on peace education within the Israeli-Palestinian context. Cohen, also Israeli, is a secular Ashkenazi Jew of European descent who identifies with a humanistic Jewish cultural framework. His academic perspective provides a critical lens for analyzing educational and cultural dynamics in peace initiatives. Together, these positionalities informed our sensitivity to the complexities of the conflict and our critical analysis of pedagogical models within a polarized society.

Findings

The initial analysis of the findings gathered in this study highlighted how the task of educating for peace revealed several pedagogical dilemmas. These included questions such as whether to address the conflict directly, whether to bring together individuals from the two different nationalities, and if so, at what stage, and whether prior preparation was necessary. From these dilemmas and challenges, several key themes emerged. The following section presents these themes, accompanied by selected excerpts from the data and relevant theoretical models that illustrate the pedagogical approaches employed by these organizations.

Four key themes emerged from the analysis:

- **Addressing the Conflict** – Each organization determines whether to engage with the conflict directly in youth activities, providing pedagogical justifications.
- **Language Barriers** – Palestinian youth often struggle with Hebrew, while Jewish youth typically do not know Arabic, creating challenges in selecting a common language for meetings.
- **Resistance & Audience** civic diversity and pluralism – The effectiveness of peace education depends on a diverse and engaged audience. Questions arise regarding participants' motivations and whether they represent a broad political and national spectrum.
- **Activities During Conflict** – Debate exists on whether peace education should continue during times of war and armed conflict, as such periods may undermine previous progress.

Addressing the Conflict

Can peace education occur without directly addressing the conflict? Meir, pedagogical director at Peace Flowers, highlighted the need to balance cultural exploration with engagement with structural and identity-based conflict: Many organizations base their discourse on politics, which is very important, but our discussions mainly focus on religion. Currently, most of the group members are Palestinians, with fewer Jews. I need to consider how to talk about the conflict without directly addressing it. However, if I only talk about hummus and falafel all day, that's also not appropriate. I need to find a balance.

He added: You understand that not everyone is a terrorist; you can enjoy their holidays and traditions. At the end of the day, while we cannot change what happens in the country or lead to a two-state solution, we can help children in Jerusalem from both sides get to know each other better.

Sylvie, a guide at the same organization, emphasized how indirect approaches foster openness:

I think it removes people's defensive walls. When people speak directly, they become defensive and try to separate from each other. When we say we came to learn about other cultures, there is more acceptance. We are not avoiding reality, but here, these are activities with children; politics won't work with them. It's also not suitable for young children to talk about peace or conflict. Although they are young, they still experience it, but they always repeat what their parents say. To enable them to be more independent thinkers, we need to give them tools and knowledge first.

Another educational approach to social justice is addressing group identity and internal community issues before confronting the conflict. Yael, a manager at Friends for Peace, explained:

In working with a group of girls, we might focus more on gender issues. It will engage them more as it speaks to their identity. The process is different but similar in Arab groups. The measures are the same, but the internal social issues are different. The story of building identity and being part of consciousness is significant. Whether it is necessarily national identity, in the Palestinian Arab identity, there are many more crises, while Jewish groups are very clear about who they are—their flag, anthem, and a strong state. In Arab groups, they are in a real identity

crisis. The national consciousness they choose to identify with has a price. So there, we empower and strengthen our identity by looking critically at processes. In Jewish groups, it's about deconstructing the narrative, and it's the opposite.

This approach was also evident in our observations of the Peace Hill program, where joint activities between Jewish and Palestinian youth avoided direct discussion of the conflict. For instance, while standing in a circle, a visible divide remained between the Jewish and Arab participants.

In contrast, some participants argued that peace education must directly address the conflict, as it equips teenagers with tools for crisis management and effective communication. Deborah from Friends for Peace emphasized:

The big goal is meaningful discourse around the conflict and significant encounters between Jewish and Palestinian youth and young adults. Meaningful means that the meeting is not just about what we have in common, friendship, and getting to know each other, but also touching on issues of disagreement and painful topics. It's very important for us to be relevant, and we never leave the conflict out of the room; it's always part of the discussion. If we ignore it and don't address it, participants will find their own way to deal with it if we don't give them tools to handle it educationally.

Yael, from the same organization, added more justifications for dealing with the conflict: Our goal is not just to get to know the other but also to undergo a political and educational process where they can look at reality both socially and develop tools to critique it. The dialogue-based encounter exposes them to another narrative, a story that is silenced. Within this, there is also recognition and reducing fear. Dialogue meetings are also political and revolve around language, the different narratives that clash, and then really managing a conversation about the elephant in the room and the conflict itself.

Miri, from Peace Hill, expanded this approach, explaining why she believes that just meeting is not enough: The contact theory is not enough. It's not just about meeting and finding common ground; we also operate from a contact approach to create a foundation of relationships and security within the group and through personal stories and bringing the conflict into the discussion through the narrative approach.

Regarding a bi-national seminar for 11th and 12th graders, she explained: "They come here for acquaintance and dialogue. They dialogue-based encounter various issues that concern society—inequality, justice, exclusion, discrimination—and they stay and discuss them together. The day-and-a-half seminar is powerful, shaking, and leaves strong feelings in them".

Mor, also from Peace Hill, described a pedagogical activity that demonstrates this as well:

After they become friends, there is an activity called "Sorry for the Question" that is just like a TV show. They split into two single-nationality groups: each group composed three questions they would like to ask the other group, dealing with specific areas: society, culture, and personal matters. Then they return to the plenary, and the rule is that the question is asked, and one or two people answer, but no one is allowed to respond back. That means you have to listen fully and respectfully to questions you might not be happy to hear. The issues come from the gut, and that's usually the turning point of these encounters.

The findings related to this theme reveal a central pedagogical tension regarding whether peace education initiatives should directly confront conflict or adopt more indirect, culturally focused approaches. Some educators, such as Meir and Sylvie from Peace Flowers, advocate for a balanced strategy that fosters intercultural understanding without immediately engaging with contentious political issues, particularly when working with young children. This approach is seen as a means to reduce defensiveness and create openness to difference. Others, like Yael from Friends for Peace, suggest that addressing internal group identities and social justice

concerns is a necessary precursor to engaging with the broader conflict. In contrast, a more critical pedagogical stance, exemplified by educators from Friends for Peace and Peace Hill, argues that meaningful peace education must directly address the conflict, providing youth with the tools to navigate difficult conversations and confront systemic inequalities. Observations of these programs further revealed a gap between organizations' declared educational goals and their actual practices, with some avoiding direct discussions despite acknowledging their importance.

Language Barriers

A second major challenge in pedagogical practice was language. Jewish adolescents often lack proficiency in Arabic, while Arab adolescents may have limited Hebrew vocabulary, depending on their age. This raised questions about which language to use and whether it matters. While bilingual activities are ideal, implementing them effectively remains a challenge. Using English as a common language was considered, but it is not always feasible, as many Arab schools do not teach it at a high level, and Jewish students also receive limited spoken English instruction. Despite these difficulties, language sometimes served as a bridge, fostering connection and exposure to something new.

In the Flowers of Peace program, organizational documents described a process facilitated by Israeli and Palestinian educators from diverse religious backgrounds, but more salient to the pedagogical process were the instructors' linguistic abilities, as meetings were conducted in Hebrew, Arabic, and English. Meir, the organization's pedagogical director, shared that:

Language is a huge challenge. Some children learn Arabic, but most Arabs do not know Hebrew, maybe a few words, especially in sixth grade. We speak a lot in English, but there are those who do not speak English, so everything is translated. Because of the language, I think about games that can be played with a limited vocabulary, for example, two groups competing to build a tower with Lego in five minutes.

In most programs, there were two instructors: one who spoke Arabic and one who spoke Hebrew. Daoud, from the Hill of Peace program, explained the importance of this: The presence of both languages is also very important. In each group, there are two facilitators – an Arab facilitator and a Jewish facilitator. The meeting opens in both Arabic and Hebrew. This helps reduce pressure, fear, and apprehension and strengthens the Arab students because they are fluent in both languages. Yael from Friends for Peace also endorsed this approach and provided an additional justification: The issue of language is important. There are Jewish participants who do not hear Arabic in their daily lives, and it sounds threatening to them. It is not something they are used to. If someone approaches us for a meeting with a single facilitator, we do not accept it.

Miri, a director at Hill of Peace, also pointed to this linguistic challenge, asserting that: It is certainly one of the challenges faced by both the participants and the guides, but it teaches a lot about listening and patience. Even if something is currently being translated into a language unrelated to me, I still need to be quiet so those who are being translated can hear and respect the translator and those who have not yet understood my joke.

She explained that the participants themselves come with stereotypes and prejudices on the subject: There is an expectation from the Jews that the Arabs will know Hebrew because it is a country where Hebrew is spoken. There is an expectation from the Arabs – why don't you understand? This raises many questions that we return to them. The Jewish-Arab narrative is also rooted in this.

Sylvie, from the Peace Flower organization, explained the opportunities that such linguistic issues raise: I remember a meeting in Jerusalem where we had to teach English and Arabic terms related to East Jerusalem and West Jerusalem. There was a very interesting discussion about the Temple Mount with the younger students. The

Arab students did not have the words to express their opinions. The Hebrew-speaking students tried to give them the terms to speak with. It was beautiful to see that despite all the difficulty and conflict, they helped each other express their views.

Language emerged as a significant pedagogical challenge within peace education initiatives, directly influencing the dynamics of intercultural encounters. The linguistic gap between Jewish and Arab adolescents, where the former often lack Arabic proficiency and the latter may have limited Hebrew skills, complicated efforts to foster meaningful dialogue. While bilingual facilitation was widely regarded as an ideal approach, implementing it effectively proved difficult, with some programs resorting to English as a common language despite its limited accessibility for many participants.

Educators addressed these challenges by incorporating nonverbal, low-language activities and ensuring the presence of facilitators fluent in both languages, a practice that was seen as critical for reducing anxiety and promoting inclusion.

At the same time, language barriers exposed underlying societal expectations and prejudices, prompting critical reflection among participants about power relations embedded in language use. The privileging of Hebrew and English in joint activities, often due to logistical convenience, reflects broader structural hierarchies within Israeli society. Arabic, though an official language, is frequently marginalized in public and educational discourse. As a result, Arab-Palestinian participants are often required to operate in a second or third language, reinforcing unequal communicative burdens and symbolic hierarchies of belonging. Despite these obstacles, language also served as a point of connection, with moments of mutual learning and cooperation arising as participants worked together to bridge their communicative gaps.

Resistance to Organizational Activities and Target Audience

These programs targeted Jewish and Arab-Palestinian teenagers nationwide, aligning with the organization's location and goals. Participation reflected a willingness to understand the other's narrative. However, interviews revealed concerns about opposition and resistance, which influenced participants' reflections on the implemented pedagogies. Meir, from the Flowers of Peace organization, shared:

There is a lot of opposition in Jerusalem, but it's not mandatory, so we don't get complaints. Those who come after school want to participate and be part of it. Some Jewish children in schools say, "Why should I meet with terrorists?" This happened to my father, and many Palestinians say this is normalization and forbidden to meet with the occupier, which hurts.

Deborah from the Friends for Peace organization described how "our biggest challenge in Jewish schools is content; not every school is interested, and there is sometimes fear of addressing controversial points."

Daoud from the Peace Hill program described opposition mainly from the Arab side:

At the beginning of the year, there were Arab youth who didn't want to meet the other side. I tried to persuade them several times; it was a democratic school, so it was an individual decision for each student. There is also opposition in the Jewish group, but less. Most want to meet, taste, see, and talk, but about 15% didn't come. There are fears, stereotypes, media influence, and parents who don't want it.

The organizations grappled with such questions, which impacted the activities.

Lana, a Palestinian facilitator from Friends for Peace, explained how:

We don't say "Palestinians," only "Arabs," because it sounds threatening. Why is it important for students to speak Arabic in meetings when the teacher doesn't agree? I wanted a joint meeting with two facilitators speaking both languages, but we had to persuade them.

It was clear that this aspect of the target audience directly influenced the programs' pedagogical reasoning. For example, Lana from Friends for Peace described how "We prepare the program for each group. If I work with a school for at-risk youth, the program looks different compared to a private school where students come from higher socioeconomic backgrounds and are generally better academically." Deborah from Friends for Peace emphasized the geographical setting in which they act, stating that:

The meetings were significant. For the first time, they asked direct questions. For example, Jews asked, "Are you angry with us?"... We dealt with silenced stories in Israeli society ... The group became a safe space for moral issues like military enlistment. We don't educate for refusal but for asking questions and giving tools for critical thinking.

Yael shared a notable example: "Once parents realized we are a Jewish-Arab organization, the youth center director had to deal with parental opposition ... participants see it as a political center where they can express political views."

The findings related to this theme highlight significant resistance to peace education initiatives, both from within participating youth populations and from the broader social environments in which these programs operate. Despite targeting Jewish and Arab-Palestinian teenagers open to engaging with the "other," opposition often shaped both participation levels and the pedagogical strategies employed. Resistance manifested in various forms, ranging from outright refusal to attend activities to parental objections and school administrators' reluctance to address controversial content. For some Jewish youth, entrenched stereotypes framed encounters with Arabs as encounters with "terrorists," while among Palestinian participants, fears of normalization and political backlash discouraged engagement. Facilitators navigated these tensions through pedagogical considerations such as adapting program content to the specific backgrounds and sensitivities of their audiences, often softening language or avoiding politically charged terms to reduce resistance. Yet, even within these constraints, moments of critical dialogue emerged, providing safe spaces for participants to confront silenced societal narratives and engage in reflective questioning about identity, justice, and coexistence.

Activities during Tense Periods

Participants offered contrasting perspectives on whether and how peace education should respond during periods of heightened political violence or armed conflict. While some organizations suspended activities, others viewed these moments as critical opportunities for deeper pedagogical engagement. Meir, the pedagogical manager at the Peace Flowers organization, explained the difficulty: "Sometimes we also cancel meetings, for example, when there was a war in Gaza or tension in Sheikh Jarrah, we did not meet because it is hard to meet during a war, and we wait until it calms down." Noor, a former instructor in the organization, added:

Once, during an emergency situation in Jerusalem, it was very difficult for them to express how they felt during the big round of violence, and I felt that although they said they were friends and tried to encourage each other, there was still something in the air that said, "We are friends as long as the situation is good. When it becomes difficult, we are not". There was a harsh atmosphere in the air. Sylvie, from the same organization, agreed, stating that "we don't want to do something that we feel is not safe. We only want to talk about it after we have thought about it after the participants have had some time to digest the events".

Conversely, at the Friends for Peace organization, the meetings continued even during tense periods, as we can learn from Deborah, who stated:

Every current event is utilized as an educational opportunity. If we ignore it and don't address it, participants will find their own ways to deal with it without educational tools. The next time a crisis occurs, all the content will evaporate, and there will be no real partnership because the routine is constantly interrupted.

Therefore, tools are essential to cope with it.

In some cases, the Arab participants expressed their tense everyday life, as expressed in meetings that were held separately by Lana from Friends for Peace:

It was a very interesting meeting where they started sharing personal stories. These are young people who find it hard to share and say they cried one day because of their ego. During that meeting, they shared that, for example, someone was arrested for having a weapon and was very scared at the police station. No one came to help him; they were used to being arrested in the middle of the night by the police. In their neighborhood, they are heroes, but no one talks to them about their fears. The purpose of the meeting was to look at themselves within the collective space they belong to critically and say what they want from this environment. To connect them to their dreams and what they would like to see in their neighborhood.

The question of whether to continue peace education activities during periods of heightened tension emerged as a critical pedagogical dilemma, reflecting divergent philosophies among organizations. Some, like Peace Flowers, preferred to suspend meetings during crises such as wars or violent incidents, prioritizing the emotional readiness and safety of participants. Educators expressed concerns that under such strained conditions, dialogue could become superficial or even counterproductive, as underlying tensions surfaced and friendships proved fragile. In contrast, organizations like Friends for Peace viewed these challenging moments as vital educational opportunities, arguing that avoiding difficult conversations during crises undermines the resilience and continuity of intergroup relationships. From this perspective, engaging directly with current events was seen as essential for equipping youth with tools to process complex realities and maintain dialogue even under stress. These meetings often created rare spaces for Arab youth to share personal stories of hardship and fear, fostering critical reflection on their lived experiences and aspirations.

These differing responses highlight an unresolved tension in peace education practice: should such programs function as spaces of psychological safety insulated from external volatility, or should they serve as civic spaces that explicitly grapple with lived political realities, even during crisis? The former treats trauma avoidance as a pedagogical imperative; the latter treats engagement with structural and existential threats as central to education for justice and resilience. The choice between these orientations reflects broader pedagogical commitments, particularly regarding whether peace education is aimed at conflict avoidance or political empowerment.

To sum, the findings presented here illuminate the multifaceted pedagogical challenges faced by peace education initiatives operating in deeply divided contexts. Central dilemmas emerged around whether and how to address the conflict directly, how to navigate linguistic barriers that both hinder and foster connection, how to contend with societal and participant resistance, and how to respond to heightened tensions during periods of crisis. These themes reveal the complex balancing act educators perform in adapting their pedagogies to diverse audiences, political sensitivities, and volatile social realities. While some approaches emphasized gradual relationship-building through indirect engagement, others advocated for confronting difficult issues head-on to foster critical awareness and resilience. These varied strategies underscore the need for a deeper theoretical understanding of the pedagogical models guiding such encounters. The following discussion introduces four theoretical frameworks that offer critical insights into the pedagogical reasoning underlying these approaches. Together, they

provide a conceptual lens through which to examine and better understand these educational practices, with relevance extending to diverse global contexts.

Discussion

These findings revealed that while the organizations shared similar overarching objectives, their pedagogical approaches varied significantly in addressing the challenges outlined above. By examining the four main themes that emerged from the data, we concentrated on two key pedagogical questions: (1) to what extent did the activities foster engagement with the conflict? and (2) What was the level of interaction between the two groups? Based on these two axes, we developed four theoretical models (Cohen, 2019) that reflect pedagogical approaches to peace education (see Figure 2). First, we will present the four models, followed by a detailed explanation of each model's pedagogical considerations and critiques (see Table 1):

- **Neither-Nor Model** – No interaction or discussion of the conflict: Organizations hold separate meetings for each nationality, focusing on unrelated topics.
- **Both-And Model** – Interaction and engagement with structural and identity-based conflict: Organizations facilitate joint meetings where both nationalities regularly address the conflict.
- **Encounter Model** – Interaction without engagement with structural and identity-based conflict: Organizations conduct joint meetings without directly discussing the conflict.
- **Conflict without Meeting Model** – engagement with structural and identity-based conflict without interaction: Organizations address the conflict within singlenationality groups as part of peace education.

The Neither-Nor Model

This educational approach to social justice conducts single-nationality activities without directly addressing conflict, aiming to prepare participants for future joint meetings. These sessions explore preliminary topics like identity, criticism, democracy, and narratives, acknowledging differences between cultural groups due to limited mutual familiarity. The model assumes prior preparation is necessary before joint discussions to align expectations and avoid overwhelming participants. Advantages include freer discussions with fewer arguments, allowing participants to raise sensitive issues they might avoid in mixed meetings. This aligns with the idea that reducing anxiety and increasing empathy fosters positive intercultural and civic contact more effectively than merely providing theoretical knowledge about the outgroup (Allport, 1954; Paluck et al., 2017). Facilitators share the participants' nationality and language, ensuring open expression. Discussions address indirectly related topics such as current affairs, civic empowerment, and racism, following the framework of indirect peace education (Bar-Tal & Rosen, 2009). The goal is to develop conflict resolution skills like empathy, reflective thinking, and exposure to diverse perspectives. Interviewees reported tailoring content to the group's community and socio-economic conditions.

This model faces criticisms, notably regarding whether peace education can be effective with only one side present. Given the deep-rooted conflict culture, Jewish education, for instance, includes militaristic narratives (Levy, 2014). Some advocate first discussing distant conflicts, as Lustig (2003) found that teaching Israeli youth about Northern Ireland altered their perspective on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. While most peace education models emphasize intercultural and civic contact to reduce stereotypes, critics argue that excessive preparation could deter youth from joint meetings.

The Both-And Model

This educational approach to social justice holds regular joint meetings where the conflict is directly addressed, supported by theories such as the contact hypothesis, confrontation model, activism, dialogue, direct model,

critical education, and narrative model. These frameworks emphasize that engaging with power dynamics raises awareness of asymmetrical relations between groups (Maoz, 2011). The model assumes that only face-to-face meetings effectively reduce stereotypes, allowing participants to engage with the other side authentically as it allows participants to critically examine both identity narratives and the structural power dynamics that underpin the conflict. Such interactions foster social connections and community partnerships, especially among geographically close youth, and develop crisis management and communication skills (Ross, 2017). Although often seen as the natural choice for peace education, this model presents significant pedagogical challenges, making it less commonly adopted. Pedagogically, it offers both difficulties and advantages, with strong support from research and field experience. Several interviewees cited their commitment to critical and narrative education as a reason for implementing this model, emphasizing that recognizing the other's narrative is essential. Key critiques concern participant readiness. Without adequate preparation, discussions may devolve into arguments, limiting meaningful engagement. Additionally, language and cultural differences pose further communication challenges.

The Encounter Model

These bi-national meetings avoid direct discussions of the conflict, instead focusing on religion, culture, and games to foster friendships, break stereotypes, and promote coexistence. This approach aligns with outdoor learning principles, emphasizing experiential activities in personal and social development (Christie & Higgins, 2012; Ford, 1986). The model assumes that young children should initially engage in shared experiences rather than conflict-related discussions, encouraging openness and reducing apprehension about intercultural and civic interactions. Findings show that activities center on games, religious events, and joint projects like films, exhibitions, and sports, demonstrating how partnerships can form despite differences. Joint music, theater, and art initiatives foster collaboration, creating a shared supra-identity and foundations for future civic cooperation across difference (Darawsheh, 2015; Maoz, 2011). These sessions are typically led by two instructors from different nationalities, with bilingual facilitation reinforcing cultural exchange.

Critics contend that avoiding conflict discussions weakens this model, particularly during heightened tensions when participants lack the tools to navigate sensitive issues by failing to address the structural conditions that sustain inequality and marginalization. This critique aligns with Payes (2017), who found that shared learning initiatives often defaulted to cultural and recreational activities, sidestepping substantive dialogue about the conflict and thereby limiting their transformative potential. Savard (2018) reinforces this concern, arguing that peace education without a focus on critical reflection and social justice risks becoming a form of 'being nice' rather than addressing systemic inequalities and the roots of conflict. These critiques echo the concerns raised in critical peace education literature. For instance, Kester (2018) and Higgins and Novelli (2020) warn that depoliticized, psycho-social approaches may stabilize rather than challenge existing inequalities. Programs that emphasize harmony over critical engagement may function as what Bekerman (2007) describes as "placebo" interventions, appearing to foster peace while avoiding deeper structural and epistemic issues.

The Conflict without Meeting Model

Activities where single-nationality groups directly engage with the conflict are rare and often arise spontaneously rather than through instructor planning. This raises the question of whether discussing the conflict within a homogeneous group is productive. Research suggests that each group maintains opposing perceptions of historical continuity and justice, and separate meetings risk reinforcing these views without exposure to the opposing narrative (Emda, Sagie, & Bar-On, 2003). The model primarily aims to strengthen the identity of the mono-

national group, often the marginalized one, by fostering open dialogue in a shared language. It assumes that such meetings allow participants to process sensitive issues before engaging in bi-national discussions.

Additionally, it helps them connect with their cultural identity through discussions, reflections on previous encounters, community activities, and topics specific to their national culture. This approach resonates with Tapper's (2015) Freirean critique of peace education models that depoliticize conflict and prioritize mutual understanding over political clarity. Programs aligned with this model emphasize critical reflection, political consciousness, and resistance as core educational goals rather than reconciliation or empathy alone.

Critics argue that this model may contradict peace education goals. Without pluralism or opposing perspectives, discussions depend heavily on facilitator guidance, potentially delegitimizing the other nationality and increasing apprehension about joint meetings. Furthermore, shared dilemmas rarely surface in these settings. While this model acknowledges the importance of internal group dialogue, critical scholars caution that such inward-facing pedagogies may inadvertently entrench exclusionary narratives. Zembylas and Bekerman (2013) argue for pedagogies that interrogate the political economy of education and challenge the institutional and discursive structures that sustain inequality. Without incorporating these dimensions, the model risks replicating the same structural violences it seeks to address.

In conclusion, these four models serve as conceptual frameworks or ideal types, offering theoretical tools for managing the tension between engagement and interaction in peace education. In practice, participants often adopted a hybrid approach, adjusting methods based on group dynamics and positioning themselves near the spectrum's midpoint. We found that the participants entered processes of peace education with preexisting ideologies, shaped by societal narratives and political discourse, as reflected in the PPP model (Gomez-Suarez, 2017).

Thus, our findings suggest that current pedagogical models in peace education vary not only in practice but in their underlying epistemological commitments. By incorporating insights from critical peace education, we argue that future pedagogies must attend not only to interpersonal dialogue but to the political, structural, and material dimensions of conflict. This requires pedagogical approaches that are both contextually grounded and reflexively critical of their own normative assumptions. We highlight the need for pedagogical strategies that not only facilitate intercultural and civic contact but also prepare participants to critically engage with the identity-based and structural dimensions of the conflict. To achieve this, rather than endorsing any single model as ideal, we emphasize the importance of ongoing reflection on both content and pedagogy while continuously navigating among the four proposed models. Our primary contribution to the discourse lies, therefore, in highlighting pedagogy as a core educational element. While recognizing the efforts of those advocating specific approaches, we stress the importance of critical reflection to support practitioners in refining their methods and actions.

Conclusions

Although this study was conducted prior to the events that now define the increasingly polarized and violent context in Israel–Palestine, namely, the October 7, 2023 terror attacks and the ongoing severe violations of human rights in Gaza resulting from the continuing armed conflict, its findings underscore the urgent need, now more than ever, for peace education initiatives to move beyond symbolic gestures of coexistence and to address the political and structural roots of inequality. Pedagogical decisions regarding language, content, and timing are not neutral; they are inherently political. Practitioners must be equipped to navigate these tensions with critical reflexivity and contextual sensitivity, especially in the current climate. Placing pedagogy at the center of this discussion enables the identification of key considerations necessary to foster meaningful and impactful

educational processes, both in Israel and in other national and international settings committed to advancing peace, justice, and reconciliation in times of both conflict and peace.

Foremost, should peace education prioritize intercultural and civic meetings? To what extent do such interactions foster openness and tolerance, and are they sufficient to encourage positive attitudes toward the other side, even without direct engagement? How can organizations promoting intercultural and civic connections contribute to peace education when the conflict is explicitly discussed? Pedagogically, can single-nationality activities alone achieve peace education goals?

Second, most organizations in this study prioritized bilingual activities, a practice essential for fostering equality and tolerance. While challenging, technological advancements are expected to ease implementation over time. Additionally, pedagogical strategies such as ice-breaking games, group exercises, and outdoor activities prove especially effective.

Third, such pedagogical considerations highlight the importance of audience composition and activity timing, particularly during periods of heightened tension. A diverse and equitable participant group, including children from various political and demographic backgrounds, is crucial. Despite challenges, conducting activities during tense periods remains essential, even if assessing their full impact is difficult. While grounded in the Israeli-Palestinian context, the conceptual models and pedagogical dilemmas identified here are relevant to contact-based peace education in other divided societies. Programs elsewhere, whether in post-conflict zones, settler-colonial contexts, or divided cities, may similarly benefit from critically examining how pedagogical structure and content relate to local histories, power asymmetries, and student positionalities?

And finally, while organizations share similar values and ideologies, comparing their foundational philosophies is crucial. Approaches like critical education, narrative education, and the contact hypothesis significantly shape pedagogical practices and require careful consideration. Ultimately, continuous reflection, on both content and delivery methods, is essential.

This research has several limitations. First, our observations did not include any binational activities that directly addressed the conflict and focused only on those that avoided it or single-national activities with a similar approach. As a result, our findings on this aspect rely solely on interviews. We believe direct observation is a valuable tool for both researchers and practitioners, enabling reflection and improvement, and we recommend that future studies prioritize observing joint activities that explicitly address the conflict. Second, the study's small sample of four organizations does not fully represent all peace education initiatives in the country. Moreover, our observations were limited to a few instances rather than sustained, long-term engagements. Future research should expand the scope by including more organizations and extended observations to provide a more comprehensive understanding of peace education practices.

The primary conclusion of this study emphasizes the importance of critically reflecting on pedagogical considerations within the field of peace education. By identifying distinct educational models and analyzing their implementation, this research underscores the necessity of balancing engagement and meaningful dialogue with the challenges presented by linguistic, cultural, and political barriers. The findings suggest that effective peace education requires continuous introspection, addressing not only program content but also the pedagogical methods employed.

References

Akar, B. (2016). Dialogic pedagogies in educational settings for active citizenship, social cohesion and peacebuilding in Lebanon. *Education, Citizenship and Social Justice*, 11(1), 44–62.

- Arató, F., & Bodnár, B. A. (2024). Narratives and common traits of peace education and the 'Teaching Students to be peacemakers' programme: Rethinking the role of cooperative learning in peace education. *Intercultural Education, 35*(5).
- Bajaj, M. (2015). 'Pedagogies of resistance' and critical peace education praxis. *Journal of Peace Education, 12*(2), 154–166.
- Bar-Tal, D. (2007). Sociopsychological foundations of intractable conflicts. *American Behavioral Scientist, 50*(11), 1430–1453.
- Bar-Tal, D., & Rosen, Y. (2009). Peace education in societies involved in intractable conflicts: Direct and indirect models. *Review of Educational Research, 79*(2), 557–575.
- Bekerman, Z. (2005). Are there children to educate for peace in conflict-ridden areas? A critical essay on peace and coexistence education. *Intercultural Education, 16*(3), 235–245.
- Bekerman, Z. (2007). Rethinking intergroup encounters: Rescuing praxis from theory, activity from education, and peace/co-existence from identity and culture. *Journal of Peace Education, 4*(1), 21–37.
- Cohen, A. (2018). Examining civic education pedagogies from a sociocultural curricular perspective: Lessons from three Israeli classrooms. *Citizenship Teaching & Learning, 13*(3), 311–327.
- Cohen, A. (2019). Typologies of citizenship and civic education: From ideal types to a reflective tool. In A. Peterson, G. Stahl, & H. Soong, *the Palgrave Handbook of Citizenship and Education* (pp. 1029–1046). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Christie, E., & Higgins, P. (2012). *The impact of outdoor learning experiences on attainment and behaviour: A brief review of literature*. University of Edinburgh.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage.
- Daaroushe, M. (2015). Dialogue-based encounter between differences: How, when, and why? *Education Policy for Democracy Dov Lautman Conference*, the Open University, Ra'anana.
- Emda, O., Sagie, S., & Bar-On, D. (2003). Social representations in action: Coping and collective defense of Jewish-Israeli and Palestinian high school students. *Megamot: Behavioral Sciences Quarterly, 42*(3), 412–436.
- Ford, P. (1986). *Outdoor education: Definition and philosophy*. ERIC Clearinghouse on Rural Education and Small Schools.
- Gomez-Suarez, A. (2017). Peace process pedagogy: Lessons from the no-vote victory in the Colombian peace referendum. *Comparative Education, 53*(3), 462–482.

- Harsh, S. (2011). Purposeful sampling in qualitative research synthesis. *Qualitative Research Journal*, 11(2), 63–75.
- Higgins, S., & Novelli, M. (2020). Rethinking peace education: A cultural political economy approach. *Comparative Education Review*, 64(1), 1–28.
- Kester, K. (2018). Coproducing peace: Beyond psychologized approaches—toward a transrational onto-epistemology and dialogic learning community as the foundations of peace education. *In Factis Pax*, 12(1), 1–24.
- Kester, K., & Cremin, H. (2017). Peace education and peace education research: Toward a concept of poststructural violence and second-order reflexivity. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 49(14), 1415–1427.
- Levy, G. (2014). Is there a place for peace education? Political education and citizenship activism in Israeli schools. *Journal of Peace Education*, 11(1), 101–119.
- Lazarus, N. (2015). Twenty years of Israeli-Palestinian peace education: A research retrospective. *Palestine-Israel Journal of Politics, Economics & Culture*, 21(2), 75–82.
- Lustig, A. (2003). *The impact of learning about a foreign conflict on changes in perception of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict* (master's thesis, University of Haifa).
- Maoz, I. (2011). Does contact work in protracted asymmetrical conflict? Appraising 20 years of reconciliation-aimed encounters between Israeli Jews and Palestinians.
- Paluck, E. L., Green, S., & Green, D. P. (2017). *The contact hypothesis re-evaluated* (SSRN Scholarly Paper No. 2973474). Social Science Research Network.
- Payes, S. (2018). Education across the divide: Shared learning of separate Jewish and Arab schools in a mixed city in Israel. *Education, Citizenship and Social Justice*, 13(1), 19–35.
- Pineda, P., Celis, J., & Rangel, L. (2019). The worldwide spread of peace education: Discursive patterns in publications and international organisations. *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, 17(5), 638–657.
- Ross, K. (2017). *Youth encounter programs in Israel: Pedagogy, identity, and social change*. Syracuse University Press.
- Ross, K. (2019). Navigating "Red Lines" and transcending the binary: Tensions in the pedagogical and political goals of peace education work. *Peace and Conflict Studies*, 26(2).
- Saldaña, J. (2009). *The coding manual for qualitative researchers*. Sage.
- Savard, M. (2018). An alternative to violence in education. *Peace and Conflict Studies*, 25(2).

Zembylas, M., & Bekerman, Z. (2013). Peace education in the present: Dismantling and reconstructing some fundamental theoretical premises. *Journal of Peace Education*, 10(2), 197–214.